

Sustainable intensification under resource constraints: Estimating the heterogeneous effects of hybrid maize adoption in Nepal

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Abstract

Managerial practices for farming-system intensification have received increased focus in research-and-development (R&D) initiatives. These technologies are proven to close the yield gaps in researcher-managed field trials and are recommended for farmer's adoption. However, not all farmers have the technical, financial, and social capital to adopt and benefit from these recommended technologies. Is the current level of productivity enhancement achieved by smallholder system intensification sufficient to sustain rural livelihoods? To this end, the study assessed the impacts of hybrid maize (*Zea mays* L.) adoption on productivity and livelihoods in the mid-hill region of Nepal. Smallholders in the study region face severe shortages of labor, improved cultivars, and inorganic fertilizers, resulting in very low yields and profitability. We find that maize hybrid adoption increased crop productivity by 109%, making the crop profitable for smallholders and enhancing the per capita food expenditure by 20%. Nevertheless, these benefits

36 were unevenly distributed: relatively small farms (≤ 0.3 ha) achieved greater gains in productivity
37 and livelihood per land unit from hybrid maize adoption, but only larger farms (> 0.3 ha) enjoyed
38 the aggregate livelihood benefits of the technology. System intensification gains economic
39 relevance because of the severe scarcity of resources, whereas the resource scarcity itself
40 determines the economic relevance of system intensification, presenting a paradox. Increasing
41 market access to material inputs did not significantly alter the observed patterns. More studies are
42 required on the relationship between farm size and the livelihood impacts of sustainable
43 intensification to facilitate R&D targeting and ensure inclusive development.

44 **Keywords:** Hybrid maize seed; Impact heterogeneity; Input constraints; Smallholder farmers;
45 Sustainable intensification; Welfare outcomes.

46 **1. Introduction**

47 The sustainable intensification of agriculture (SIA) is broadly defined as the process of producing
48 more output from the same land area without damaging the environment while improving
49 livelihoods and food security (Rudel 2020; Godfray and Garnett 2014). The enhancement of
50 system productivity through the efficient use of marketed inputs and natural resources forms the
51 core of many SIA approaches (Haile et al. 2017). Some of the technologies useful for closing yield
52 gaps through system intensification rely on the timely availability of quality external inputs, for
53 example, herbicides for weed management in conservation agriculture (CA) systems (Bouwman
54 and Giller 2020). Insufficient market access to critical inputs in many regions of the Global South,
55 therefore, often impedes technological change (Guo, Ola, and Benjamin 2020).

56 There is rich socioeconomic literature on the adoption and impacts of SIA technologies in maize
57 systems, with several dozen papers published annually (Garcia and Krishna 2021; Kubitza and
58 Krishna 2020). However, most of these studies are confined to sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), and
59 there is a significant information gap on the status and challenges faced by the maize farmers of
60 South and Southeast Asia. In the recent past, many Asian countries have expanded maize

61 production and diversified its use from food to the feed and fuel sectors, and maize has assumed
62 the status of a cash crop in this region (Shiferaw et al. 2011). System intensification with hybrid
63 maize technology necessitates well-developed input and output supply chains (Mango et al. 2018;
64 Alia 2017), and the timely availability of quality inputs, especially inorganic fertilizers, labor, and
65 credit, is a prerequisite to ensuring an efficient production process (Alene and Hassan 2006;
66 Ghimire and Huang 2015). However, the agriculture of several developing countries of South and
67 Southeast Asia in general, and Nepal in particular, is characterized by poorly developed seed
68 systems (Gauchan 2019; Spielman and Kennedy 2016), a constrained supply of inorganic
69 fertilizers (Ward et al. 2020), small and fragmented farms (Niroula and Thapa 2007), and input
70 shortages, resulting in high cultivation costs (Paudel et al. 2019). These factors could limit the
71 scope of the sustainable intensification of maize systems using hybrids as a technology component.

72 Compared to open-pollinated varieties (OPVs), hybrid maize possesses a high genetic yield
73 potential due to heterosis (Flint-Garcia et al. 2009). Hybrid vigor drops with the reuse of farm-
74 saved seeds, resulting in a perpetual market demand for seed that attracts private seed companies
75 (Spielman and Kennedy 2016; Raghu et al. 2015). Although hybrid maize is promoted and widely
76 cultivated across several developing countries as a sustainable intensification technology due to
77 its high land productivity potential and high nutrient-use efficiency (Devkota et al., 2016), the
78 relative benefits of the technology are dependent upon the local agro-climatic and market
79 conditions (Kathage et al. 2015; Alene and Hassan 2006). Because not many socioeconomic
80 evaluations of maize production technologies have been carried out in South Asia in the last decade
81 (Krishna et al. 2019; Garcia and Krishna 2021), we hardly know anything about the relative
82 advantage of adopting hybrid seeds in countries like Nepal. Some of the experimental trials
83 conducted in Nepal confirmed that maize farmers could improve land productivity by switching

84 from local OPVs to hybrids (Devkota et al. 2016; 2015). However, these experimental trials are
85 inadequate for shedding light on the biophysical and socioeconomic impacts of the technology
86 across diverse farm types and production environments. Against this backdrop, the present study
87 examined the adoption and impacts of hybrid maize among smallholder farmers of the mid-hills
88 of Nepal, where maize grain is primarily used for household consumption. We hypothesize that
89 the impacts of the technology on productivity and farmers' livelihoods are heterogeneous due to
90 the severity of resource constraints and differential access to input markets.

91 The unique situation of Nepalese agriculture that shapes farmers' adoption of new technologies is
92 discussed in the next section (Section 2). The data collection methods, summary of data used for
93 the empirical analysis, and analytical framework are provided in Section 3. The empirical results
94 are presented and discussed in Section 4. The last section (Section 5) concludes the study and
95 provides policy recommendations.

96 **2. Resource constraints and the history of hybrid maize dissemination in Nepal**

97 Despite being an agrarian economy, with two-thirds of its population dependent on agriculture for
98 livelihood (MoAD 2017; World Bank 2020), food insecurity is rampant in Nepal. Two-thirds of
99 Nepal's districts face food shortages every year (Joshi, Conroy, and Witcombe 2012), and a quarter
100 of the population lives in absolute poverty (NPC 2017). Among the three distinct agro-ecological
101 zones of the country, food insecurity is most pronounced in the mid-hill and mountain regions
102 (Karki et al. 2015). Low agricultural productivity due to the low adoption of modern production
103 technologies has been identified as the primary reason for food insecurity and high poverty in the
104 region (Bairagi, Mishra, and Giri 2019; Ghimire and Huang 2015). The adoption of technologies,

105 such as hybrid maize, has the potential to improve food security and reduce rural poverty in Nepal
106 by increasing crop productivity and profitability.

107 Maize is one of Nepal's major cereal crops, where it is grown for food, feed, and fodder (Bahadur
108 et al., 2014; Tiwari et al., 2009). The average domestic consumption of maize grain as food in
109 Nepal is about 3 kilograms per person per month (Ranum, Peñ-a-Rosas, and Garcia-Casal 2014),
110 and a substantial portion is also dedicated to livestock production (Paudel et al. 2014). The use of
111 maize grain differs widely across agro-ecological regions. In the mid-hills and mountains, it is
112 mainly used for human consumption, unlike in the Terai region, where maize is primarily used for
113 industrial purposes (e.g., for making poultry feed) (KC et al. 2015; CBS 2015). Domestic demand
114 cannot be met with the current level of maize production in Nepal. The average maize yield of
115 Nepal is 2.6 tons/ha (as of 2018), which is less than half the global average (FAO 2020; MoAD
116 2017). Low crop productivity and high demand necessitate the import of maize (Timsina, Ghimire,
117 and Lamichhane 2016).

118 The history of hybrid maize adoption is relatively recent in Nepal. In 2003, the National Maize
119 Research Program (NMRP) released the first maize hybrid ("Gaurav Hybrid") (SQCC 2013),
120 recommended for cultivation in the lowland agroecology (altitude <600 m). Since then, seven
121 hybrids have been developed and released by the NMRP in collaboration with the International
122 Maize and Wheat Improvement Center (CIMMYT). However, hybrid seed production has taken
123 place at a slow pace in the country, with a limited quantity of seed commercially available in the
124 market (Adhikari 2014). Furthermore, "Gaurav Hybrid" did not become popular with maize
125 farmers (SQCC 2013). Between 2010 and 2018, about 61 hybrid maize cultivars were registered
126 by the Government of Nepal (SQCC 2019), of which only eight were developed domestically.
127 With an increasing demand for hybrid maize seed by farmers and a shortage of domestic supply,

128 in 2011, the government liberalized the hybrid maize seed market, which presented an opportunity
129 for regional seed companies to enter the Nepalese market and formally register maize hybrids.ⁱ

130 The reduction of dependence on cereal imports, including maize, has gained high political
131 importance, as evidenced in the Government of Nepal’s Agriculture Development Strategy (2015-
132 2035) and Seed Sector Development Strategy (SQCC 2013).ⁱⁱ These strategies emphasize the
133 intensification of internal productivity through developing and deploying high-yielding hybrids,
134 improvements in crop management, and the efficient use of fertilizers. However, the country’s
135 ability to intensify maize productivity is affected by the constrained access to production inputs
136 (Figure 1). Firstly, the Nepalese agriculture sector is suffering from an acute labor shortage due to
137 the increasing trend of labor out-migration, which has increased five-fold in recent years from the
138 year 2000 (Figure 1a). This accelerating trend of domestic labor loss has sharply increased rural
139 wages (more than doubled between 2002 and 2017) (Figure 1b). Rising rural wages due to labor
140 shortages have sharply increased production costs of all crops. Secondly, the average household
141 landholding size has been reduced by 36% (Figure 1e), and the per capita landholding reduced by
142 31% during the last three decades (Figure 1d). Thirdly, due to a nascent national seed system, the
143 country relies heavily on imported hybrid maize seed, while the demand for hybrid maize seed has
144 expanded from 20 tons in 2008 to 1,410 tons in 2017 (Figure 1c). This high dependence on the
145 import of hybrid seed has created a trade deficit of almost US\$ 4 million (Figure 1f) from the
146 maize seed sector alone. Moreover, the price of the imported hybrid seed is high, and resource-
147 constrained farmers may be unable to purchase a sufficient quantity of seed, limiting the scope of
148 maize system intensification. Finally, due to underdeveloped industries, Nepal currently imports
149 all inorganic fertilizers from other countries. Although the overall import of inorganic fertilizers,

150 such as urea, di-ammonium phosphate (DAP), and potash, has drastically increased during the last
151 two decades (Figure 1g–i), it can only fulfill <50% of the current domestic demand.

152 [\[Figure 1 here\]](#)

153 **3. Methodology**

154

155 **3.1. Data**

156 The basis of this empirical study is a farm-household survey dataset collected from Nepal’s mid-
157 hill region’s villages during October-November 2017. Face-to-face interviews using a structured
158 questionnaire were implemented with a computer-assisted personal interview (CAPI) software,
159 with several validation rules to minimize data entry errors and survey time. The questionnaire
160 elicited information on the household’s socioeconomic status, cropping systems, inputs for maize
161 cultivation and outputs, and sources of household income and expenditure.

162 The data came from six districts from the mid-hills of Nepal: Doti, Surkhet, Palpa, Nuwakot,
163 Kavre, and Illam, which were purposively selected based on the area under maize cultivation. The
164 location of the selected districts is shown in [Figure 2](#). The district-level maize acreage was
165 quantified in consultation with the District Agriculture Development Offices, key informants, and
166 agricultural input dealers (e.g., agro-vets, who sell maize seed to farmers). According to the
167 Agriculture Knowledge Centers of the Government of Nepal, about 6.02% of the maize area was
168 cultivated with hybrid seeds in the selected districts ([Appendix Table A1](#)). In each district, the area
169 under maize and the extent of hybrid maize adoption in sub-districts (Village Development
170 Committees or VDCs) were estimated based on the area under maize cultivation and an initial
171 estimation of hybrid maize adoption among farmers. A total of 34 VDCs were purposively
172 selected, and 731 maize-growing farm-households were randomly selected from these VDCs for

173 the survey. Here, we define hybrid maize adopters as farm-households that cultivated hybrid maize
174 in any of their plots in 2017.ⁱⁱⁱ About 43% of sample households were adopters of the technology,
175 and their over-representation was necessary for impact estimation, which was ensured through the
176 purposive selection of VDCs.

177 [\[Figure 2 here\]](#)

178 **3.2. Empirical framework**

179 As economic agents, farmers are often assumed to be resource-constrained and rational, attempting
180 to maximize their yields and profits through the judicious use of scarce resources like land, labor,
181 and material inputs. Under this assumption, farmers adopt hybrid maize technology based on
182 whether the expected benefit from adoption is higher than the non-adoption status quo (OPV
183 cultivation) (Abdoulaye and Wossen 2018; Jaleta et al. 2018; Mishra et al. 2016; Mishra, Khanal,
184 and Pede 2017; Mishra et al. 2018; Shiferaw et al. 2014). For the empirical analysis, we restrict
185 our analysis to monetary benefits, although non-monetary benefits (e.g., consumption utility) can
186 also play a crucial role in determining farmers' adoption decisions (Krishna et al. 2013).

187 Let us assume that \hat{Y} is the difference in the net gain in the outcome variables between hybrid
188 maize adopters and non-adopters. Then, $\hat{Y} > 0$ implies that the adoption of hybrid maize is more
189 beneficial to the farmer than non-adoption. However, \hat{Y} cannot be observed directly and can only
190 be expressed as the function of observed farm-level socioeconomic attributes in a latent model
191 (details of the empirical framework are provided as [Supplementary Materials Text](#)). However,
192 estimating the causal effect of hybrid adoption on the selected outcome indicators (e.g., maize
193 productivity) is difficult due to the likelihood of an endogeneity problem. Finding the “true causal
194 effect” of the technology adoption on key outcome indicators requires controlling observed and

195 unobserved sources of heterogeneity between technology adopters and non-adopters (Wooldridge
196 2010; Angrist and Pischke 2009). Technology adopters and non-adopters may differ in their
197 inherent individual skills and abilities. Failure to account for these heterogeneities may bias
198 parameter estimates and result in false inferences. In this regard, the use of the ordinary least
199 squares (OLS) method that can control only the observed heterogeneities while estimating the
200 effect of technology adoption may lead to biased estimates. In this study, we used an endogenous
201 switching regression (ESR) with a selection instrument to account for both sources of
202 heterogeneity. To estimate the causal effect using ESR, the selection instrument should affect
203 outcome indicators – maize productivity, gross margin, and per capita food expenditure (PCFE) –
204 *only* through hybrid adoption. With the help of the instrumental variable, the ESR addresses the
205 problem of endogeneity by estimating the selection equation with a binary adoption variable (first
206 stage) and the outcome equation with a continuous variable (second stage) simultaneously,
207 employing the full information maximum-likelihood estimation approach (Lokshin and Sajaia
208 2004).

209 The instrumental variable used in this study is the number of years (duration) of availability of
210 hybrid maize seed at the local input dealers. Local availability of the technology determines its
211 adoption but might not affect the outcome variables directly. We assume that other farmers in the
212 village gradually started adopting hybrid maize with the availability of the technology (hybrid seed
213 at the village dealers) after witnessing the productivity gains in adopted farms. Nevertheless, one
214 may assume that the duration of hybrid seed availability at the local dealers might not affect maize
215 productivity, gross margin, and PCFE unless the technology is adopted. However, it is imperative
216 to rule out the possibility that general economic development in the village does *not* determine
217 both input supply chain formation and farmer income (Kubitza and Krishna 2020). We included

218 regional dummies and distance to input markets from households to capture the differences in the
219 general economic development of the locality. Furthermore, we verified the suitability of our
220 instrument by conducting a simple falsification test, following Di Falco et al. (2011). A good
221 instrumental variable would be strongly associated with hybrid adoption but not with the outcome
222 indicators for non-adopters. This instrument falsification test suggested that our instrument
223 satisfied the exclusion restriction for productivity and PCFE but not for profitability ([Appendix](#)
224 [Table A2](#)).

225 We estimated the average treatment effects on the treated (ATT) for the hybrid maize adopters and
226 the average treatment effects on the untreated (ATU) for the non-adopters from ESR models.
227 Furthermore, following Di Falco et al. (2011), we estimated the heterogeneity effects; hybrid
228 maize adopters may have a different socioeconomic profile than non-adopters, shaping the impact
229 magnitude. Further details of the empirical framework are provided as [Supplementary Materials](#)
230 [Text](#).

231 **4. Results and discussion**

232 **4.1. Descriptive statistics**

233 The summary statistics of the input and output variables disaggregated by hybrid maize adopters
234 ($n = 311$) and non-adopters ($n = 420$) are presented in [Table 1](#), while the detailed maize enterprise
235 budget is presented in [Appendix Table A3](#). The seed cost for the hybrid adopters was about five
236 times higher (NPR 8,665 or US\$ 83 per ha) than for non-adopters (NPR 1,731 or US\$ 17 per ha),
237 and this could be one of the major limiting factors for hybrid maize dissemination among poor
238 farm-households of the mid-hills of Nepal. Hybrid maize adopters also applied inorganic fertilizers
239 at a significantly higher rate. Labor costs were also high, but the expenditure for land preparation

240 (particularly the cost of tillage operations) was lower for adopters. The lower land preparation cost
241 for adopters could be associated with mechanized tillage instead of human or animal traction. Due
242 to higher expenditure on material costs and human labor, the total variable cost for hybrid adopters
243 was significantly higher: on average, NPR 74,299 (US\$ 714) per hectare for adopters against NPR
244 60,380 (US\$ 581) per hectare for non-adopters. On the other hand, maize productivity was 93%
245 higher (at 4,370 kg per ha) for hybrid maize adopters than for non-adopters (at 2,261 kg per ha).
246 Albeit with higher variable costs, gains in crop productivity enabled hybrid adopters to secure a
247 significantly higher gross margin (NPR 28,773 or US\$ 277 per ha) than non-adopters, who were
248 losing money (gross margin NPR -2,930 or US\$ -28 per ha) on average. However, due to the
249 small farm size (0.27 ha), the average incremental household income gain from hybrid adoption
250 was relatively modest (NPR 7,769 or US\$ 75). Adopting farm-households had a 29% higher PCFE
251 (NPR 13,093 or US\$ 126) than non-adopting ones (NPR 10,175 or US\$ 98).^{iv}

252 [Table 1 here]

253 Selected socioeconomic attributes of hybrid maize adopters and non-adopters are presented in
254 [Table 2](#) and further details in [Appendix Table A4](#). The average farm size for maize growers in the
255 study area was 0.42 ha, and the farm size was not statistically different between adopters and non-
256 adopters. However, on average, the adopters had a slightly larger area under maize cultivation
257 (0.27 ha) than the non-adopters (0.25 ha). The hybrid adopters had more years of experience in
258 cultivating maize. Among the adopters, the percentage of male household heads (87%) was higher
259 among adopters than that of non-adopters (82%), and they were located closer to input markets
260 (5.67 km) than the non-adopters (9.53 km). Closeness to markets could be one of the main drivers
261 of the adoption of hybrid maize and the increased use of material inputs, including inorganic
262 fertilizers. Moreover, the number of years since maize hybrid was first introduced in the village

263 agro-vet (private input dealers) stores was significantly higher for hybrid maize adopters than for
264 non-adopters. Finally, geographic differences were also observed for the adoption of hybrid maize.
265 There was a higher rate of adoption in the central hills, as compared to the eastern and mid-western
266 hill districts of Nepal.

267 [\[Table 2 here\]](#)

268 [Table 2](#) also contains a summary of variables, such as a farmer's age, education, caste, and primary
269 occupation, across the two adoption categories. In the adopter group, the share of households
270 belonging to the socially non-marginalized castes (such as *Chhetry* and *Brahmin*) was high at 61%.
271 Among non-adopters, the difference between the share of households belonging to marginalized
272 castes (such as *Dalits* and *Janajatis*; 52%) and that of non-marginalized castes (48%) was
273 statistically insignificant. There was no notable difference in perceived labor scarcity among
274 adopters and non-adopters, but hybrid adopters were found to secure labor by providing higher
275 wages for farming operations. A significantly higher percentage of adopters reported difficulty in
276 finding draft animals for agricultural land preparation, leading to the increased use of mechanized
277 tillage. Although there were no detectable differences in off-farm income, a higher percentage of
278 adopters' farms had concrete houses, indicating that relatively wealthy households adopted hybrid
279 maize ([Table 1](#)).

280 **4.2. Adoption of hybrid maize in the mid-hills of Nepal and its implications**

281 The key results from the ESR model estimates for maize productivity, profitability, and PCFE are
282 presented in [Table 3](#), and the full models in [Appendix Tables A5-A7](#). The ESR method employed
283 jointly estimated the selection equation in the first stage and the outcome equation in the second
284 stage, as specified in the empirical framework section. The empirical estimation of the selection

285 equation can be interpreted as that of normal probit coefficients. In [Appendix Tables A5-A7](#), we
286 also provide the OLS coefficients, in which the coefficient of hybrid maize adoption was found to
287 be positive and statistically significant. Nevertheless, the correlation between the error term in the
288 selection equation and the outcome equation was different from zero in the ESR model on maize
289 productivity, indicating the existence of selection bias in using OLS (Lokshin and Sajaia, 2004).
290 The correlation between the gross margin and the PCFE in the ESR framework, however, was not
291 statistically significant, indicating the absence of selection bias in these models. We kept the ESR
292 estimates, however, and derived treatment effects to gain insights into the heterogeneous effects
293 of hybrid maize adoption with respect to key socioeconomic variables, viz., landholding size, and
294 market access.

295 [\[Table 3 here\]](#)

296 Household heads with a higher number of years of experience in maize cultivation, farms where a
297 higher rate of inorganic fertilizers in maize was applied, and households that paid high agricultural
298 labor wages had a greater probability of adopting maize hybrids. Farm households that possessed
299 concrete houses increasingly adopted hybrids. Farmers with better market access were found to
300 have a higher chance of adoption. The instrumental variable – the duration of availability of hybrid
301 maize seed with the local trader – was also statistically significant and positive. Finally, spatial
302 heterogeneity in hybrid maize adoption was evident from the significant regional dummies in the
303 selection models ([Appendix Tables A5-A7](#)). We do not over-interpret the adoption estimates, as
304 our primary goal is to examine the impacts of adoption, and the selected models with binary
305 dependent variables have severe limitations with regard to capturing the complex decision-making
306 process concerning technology adoption (Glover, Sumberg, and Andersson 2016; Garcia and
307 Krishna 2021).

308 The rest of [Table 3](#) and [Appendix Tables A5-A7](#) include the key estimates on maize productivity
309 per ha, gross margin per ha, and PCFE for hybrid maize adopters and non-adopters, respectively.
310 Farm size was negatively associated with maize productivity, indicating the higher productivity of
311 small farms compared with large farms. In the literature, there is plenty of evidence for highly
312 productive small farms, owing to better crop management (Carter 1984; Bardhan 1973; Chand,
313 Prasanna, and Singh 2017; Wu et al. 2018). However, in our case, most sample farms were in the
314 marginal farm category, with 93% farms operating under 1 ha, and hence better crop management
315 could not be the only reason for the high productivity of smaller farms. Furthermore, the coefficient
316 of farm size was positive (0.14) for non-adopters in the model, with the gross margin per ha as the
317 dependent variable. Similarly, farm size was positively associated with PCFE among adopters:
318 with a 1% increase in farm size, the PCFE of hybrid maize adopters increased by about 0.24%.
319 Land was not only a factor of production but also an asset facilitating access to working capital,
320 and hence had a conflicting role in enhancing productivity and profitability. Furthermore, the
321 smallest farmers of the Nepal hills might be able to acquire production inputs in small doses, as
322 required, increasing not only maize productivity but also the variable cost of production.

323 In the ESR outcome equations, we included some but not all possible indicators of input scarcity.
324 The included ones were found to limit maize productivity. The productivity of hybrid maize
325 adopters who faced difficulties finding human labor was lower by 11%, and of non-adopters by
326 17% ([Appendix Table A5](#)).^y This variable also had a significant negative effect on the household's
327 PCFE. This finding is consistent with earlier studies in Nepal that showed that labor out-migration
328 and shortages caused a significant delay in crop establishment and farm operations and had a
329 negative effect on crop productivity (Khanal 2018; Khanal et al. 2015; Maharjan, Bauer, and Knerr
330 2013b; 2013a). Moreover, the marginal effects on productivity of inorganic fertilizers for hybrid

331 maize adopters and non-adopters were similar, although the former applied more fertilizers and
332 had higher nitrogen-use efficiency (Devkota et al., 2016). Finally, an increase in the labor wage
333 rate was found to be negatively associated with maize profitability for both adopters and non-
334 adopters, which was not surprising. However, a positive association between the wage rate and
335 PCFE existed. Most farm households hired out their labor, and a higher wage rate enhanced
336 household income and hence food consumption.

337 The estimates of the impact of hybrid maize adoption on maize productivity, gross margin per
338 hectare, and PCFE are presented in [Table 4](#), together with the OLS estimates. The marginal effect
339 of the OLS estimates after transformation included a 74% increase in maize productivity, a 34%
340 increase in gross margins per hectare, and a 14% increase in PCFE. The ESR values also showed
341 significantly higher benefits for technology adoption. Here, we reported the ATT and ATU values
342 for adopters and non-adopters separately. The ATT values capture the difference in the outcome
343 variables for hybrid adopters between the current estimates (with the adoption of the technology),
344 and the estimates, had they not adopted it. Similarly, the ATU values show the difference between
345 the current estimates and the outcomes of the non-adopters had they adopted the technology. The
346 estimates showed that the adoption of hybrid maize has a significant and positive impact on maize
347 productivity, gross margins, and PCFE for adopting households. It would also have been beneficial
348 for non-adopters had they adopted maize hybrids.

349 For adopters, the adoption of hybrid maize enabled the sample households to increase maize
350 productivity by 109% and PCFE by 20%. For non-adopters, adoption would have increased
351 productivity by 66% and PCFE by 64%. Maize cultivation in the study area was not profitable for
352 non-adopters, and this would also have been the case had adopters not adopted the technology.

353

[Table 4 here]

354 Despite the statistically significant, positive ATT estimates, the crop income accrued to the
355 household due to adoption was not high (NPR 10,622 or US\$ 102) for sustaining a rural household
356 due to the small size of farm-holding. This could be one of the reasons for the relatively small
357 increase in PCFE (NPR 1,982 or US\$ 19 per household) for adopters. More research is required
358 on whether this increase has helped farmers to cross over the poverty threshold. In the case of non-
359 adopters, however, the use of maize hybrids could help them avoid financial losses from crop
360 production. Hybrid maize adopters and non-adopters were systematically different, as indicated
361 by the transitional heterogeneity (TH) estimates in Table 4, and a direct comparison of the impacts
362 of hybrid maize on adopters and non-adopters without addressing the observed and unobserved
363 heterogeneities would lead to biased estimates. In contrast, the positive and statistically significant
364 values of TH for productivity and gross margin ($ATT > ATU$) showed that hybrid maize adopters
365 had the potential to realize higher productivity and gross margin. For PCFE, however, $ATU >$
366 ATT , possibly because non-adopters face negative returns in the absence of the technology.

367 We checked the robustness of our findings using the Inverse Probability Weighted Regression
368 Adjusted (IPWRA) method.^{vi} The results are presented in Table 5. Consistent with the results from
369 the ESR, the treatment effects for hybrid maize adoption on maize productivity, gross margin, and
370 PCFE were statistically significant. The IPWRA results show that the adoption of maize hybrids
371 increased crop productivity, gross margins, and PCFE by 1,586 kg/ha, NPR by 25,972 per ha (US\$
372 250), and NPR by 1,747 (US\$ 17), respectively. However, the impact magnitude was lower than
373 that estimated in the ESR framework, possibly because unobserved heterogeneity was not
374 accounted for in the IPWRA method.

375

[Table 5 here]

376 In sum, the OLS and ESR estimates presented in this section clearly indicate the significant
377 positive productivity, gross margins, and welfare (i.e., PCFE) effects of hybrid maize adoption,
378 even if farmers have several resource constraints. While our findings are similar to the studies
379 conducted in other regions (Becerril and Abdulai 2010; Abdoulaye and Wossen 2018; Mathenge,
380 Smale, and Olwande 2014; Ahmed et al. 2017; Manda and Alene 2018; Jaleta et al. 2018; Kassie,
381 Jaleta, and Mattei 2014), they also indicate that transition to maize hybrid technology will have
382 modest benefits for smallholder farm-households working under severe resource constraints.
383 Given that the per capita land availability in Nepal is less than 0.12 ha (Figure 1), that maize is
384 only one of several crops cultivated in the farming systems, and that the hybrid maize technology
385 could increase gross margins by US\$ 378 per ha (US\$ 45 per capita per season; ATT from Table
386 4), more assessments are required on the potential of the technology to reduce poverty and food
387 insecurity in the mid-hill region of Nepal. The effects of technology on the livelihoods of
388 agricultural laborers should also be examined. Due to the heightened demand for human labor with
389 adoption, the technology may also be beneficial for the labor-providing households of Nepal.

390 **4.3. Heterogeneous effects of hybrid maize adoption**

391 Technology adoption among maize farmers may have differential impacts across different
392 socioeconomic strata, depending on the degree of resource scarcity that the farmers face. To
393 examine these heterogeneous effects, we stratified the data into different categories by (a) farm-
394 size quartiles and (b) farmers' access to input markets. The results for the heterogeneous effects of
395 hybrid maize adoption across these two categorical variables are presented in Tables 6 and 7.

396

[Table 6 and Table 7 here]

397 To assess the impacts of hybrid maize adoption on productivity, gross margin per ha, and PCFE
398 across different farm sizes, we stratified the sample into four farm-size quartiles (Table 6). An
399 inter-quantile ATT comparison shows unique patterns, demonstrating that the livelihood impacts
400 of hybrid seed adoption are crucially dependent on the resource status. The same holds true for
401 ATU. While the impacts of hybrid maize adoption on maize productivity and gross margins (for
402 both ATT and ATU) across all the farm-sized quartiles were statistically significant at the 1% level
403 for the adopting farms, the magnitude of the effects of the hybrid technology on productivity and
404 gross margins (NPR per ha) was considerably higher for the first quartile farms; the size of the
405 effect diminished in the third and fourth quartiles. On the other hand, the treatment effects of
406 hybrid maize adoption on PCFE for the adopters' farms were positive and statistically significant
407 only in the third and fourth quartile farms. The non-significant livelihood effects of hybrid maize
408 adoption could be associated with a smaller area allocated to maize in the first and second quartile
409 farms (an average of 0.15 ha) than in the third and fourth quartile (0.35 ha) farms. Irrespective of
410 the high agronomic potential of hybrid maize technology, a certain minimum landholding size is
411 required for its livelihood impacts to be manifested.

412 To assess the impacts of hybrid maize adoption across different farm sizes and levels of market
413 access, we stratified our data into low and high access to a market with respect to large and small
414 farms (Table 7). The impacts of hybrid maize adoption on maize productivity and gross margins
415 were statistically significant, irrespective of the level of market access. Hybrid maize adoption did
416 not enhance the PCFE of the smallest farms across both high and low market-access categories.
417 This could, again, be due to the low level of household net economic benefit (i.e., gross margin
418 per household) obtained by the smallest farms. Nevertheless, the PCFE of the largest farms was

419 statistically significant across both the high and low market-access categories. The treatment effect
420 results (ATU) were similar for non-adopters, which suggests that hybrid maize adopters across the
421 small farm-size categories, with or without market access, did not benefit with respect to PCFE.
422 In the context of Nepal, results suggest that farm size is a much more important determinant of
423 livelihood effects than access to an input market.

424 **5. Conclusion and policy implications**

425 Farmers of rural Nepal face a constrained supply of several marketed inputs and natural resources,
426 making the sustainable intensification of cereal systems a challenging endeavor. By examining
427 hybrid maize adoption as a case of sustainable intensification by the smallholder farmers of
428 Nepal's rainfed mid-hills, we tested the hypothesis that adoption of this technology enhances
429 productivity, profitability, and household welfare, depending on factors such as the scale of
430 operation. The current Nepalese context of rising on-farm wages (due mainly to labor out-
431 migration), fragmented landholdings, high dependency on maize hybrid seed imports, and limited
432 availability of inorganic fertilizers provides ample opportunities to test the aforementioned
433 hypothesis. Our findings revealed that the constrained availability of material inputs such as
434 inorganic fertilizers, on-farm wage rates (labor scarcity), and market proximity were strongly
435 associated with farmers' adoption of maize hybrids. Moreover, the adoption of maize hybrids
436 increased on-farm productivity and profitability overall. However, we also found that hybrid maize
437 adoption had heterogeneous effects, with relatively larger farms (the upper 50%, above 0.3 ha)
438 benefiting from adoption in terms of gains in productivity, profitability, and welfare outcomes.
439 Smaller farms (the lower 50%, below 0.3 ha) did not benefit with respect to welfare outcomes,
440 although they were more productive than the larger farms. Even with increased market access, the
441 scenario remains unaltered.

442 We derived three major policy implications for the smallholder farming systems in Nepal, which
443 are not strictly in line with recommendations from previous studies on cereal system
444 intensification. For example, Spielman et al. (2010) focused on opening up the input market as a
445 precondition for the intensification of cereal systems in Ethiopia. However, our findings suggest a
446 public-private partnership in R&D programs on sustainable intensification. A single and piece-
447 wise intervention, a common method of disseminating proprietary technologies, is insufficient to
448 improve rural livelihoods. R&D programs and government policies should target the diffusion of
449 multiple sustainable intensification technologies, ensuring input access and addressing
450 fundamental resource constraints. While the private sector plays a key role in making the
451 technologies available, facilitating the adoption of multiple interventions requires public R&D and
452 extension support. Only a multi-layering of technologies would offset the adverse effects of
453 resource shortages. The incremental effect of technology combinations was observed earlier by
454 Marenya et al. (2020), who showed that the fertilizer-dominant intensification strategy provided
455 only a 30% incremental yield, whereas the combination of fertilizer, maize-legume diversification,
456 and soil and water conservation provided an 88% incremental yield. It is expected that technology
457 combinations are also likely to have highly positive returns in terms of profitability and rural
458 livelihoods in countries like Nepal. This is our first recommendation derived from the empirical
459 analysis.

460 Secondly, policies and R&D strategies aimed at targeting sustainable intensification technologies
461 across farming communities should be developed. Takeshima et al. (2017) showed that an in-depth
462 understanding of the returns from inputs is critical in formulating effective policies for the
463 dissemination of agricultural inputs in developing countries. However, we found that the benefits
464 to the adoption of hybrid maize varied widely across socioeconomic strata. Sample farmers with

465 the smallest landholdings, despite being more productive, were unable to sustain their livelihoods
466 (i.e., PCFE) from maize cultivation alone. More research is needed on the differential access to
467 production resources across social groups and its implications for economic inequality. For
468 example, the nature of our dataset does not allow us to examine the role of social marginalization
469 with respect to gender. Burke and Jayne (2021) showed an association between social
470 marginalization and low input quality: women farmers of Africa were found to be more likely to
471 farm with lower quality seed and less fertilizer on marginal land. In Nepal, more studies need to
472 be carried out on the roles played by male out-migration and the feminization of Nepalese
473 agriculture on productivity and farm income.

474 Finally, smallholder farmers in the mid-hills of Nepal should be encouraged towards income
475 diversification, and options should be provided to divert them towards alternative farming systems
476 such as the vegetable or dairy sectors for the betterment of rural livelihoods. Despite such system
477 diversification, a small landholding size might sometimes not be sufficient for households to raise
478 themselves out of poverty. There have not been many studies made on the role of non-farm income
479 in rural livelihoods in Nepal. However, studies conducted in other parts of the Global South are
480 also valid here. Holden et al. (2004) observed that unconstrained access to low-wage, non-farm
481 employment could improve household income more substantially than the provision of
482 unconstrained access to credit for the purchase of farm inputs in the Ethiopian highlands; this
483 observation is particularly relevant for the resource-constrained farming conditions of the mid-
484 hills of Nepal. The structural transformation of the country requires more research and policy
485 attention.

486 **Acknowledgments**

487 This study was conducted as part of the project “Cereal System Initiatives for South Asia”
488 (CSISA). The project is supported by the United States Agency for International Development
489 (USAID) and the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation (BMGF). We gratefully thank the farmers
490 for their time in participating in the survey, Anish Dahal, Bivek Acharya, Kiran Dahal, and
491 Sameer Shrestha for conducting the interviews with farmers, and Elizabeth Waygood for language
492 editing. This paper reflects the authors’ views and not those of USAID, BMGF, CSISA, or authors’
493 organizations.

494 **Declaration of interest statement**

495 No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

496 **Funding**

497 This work was supported by the [United States Agency for International Development (USAID)]
498 under Grant [BFS-G-11-00002] and [Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation (BMGF)] under Grant
499 [OPP1133205].

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710

711 **End Notes:**

ⁱ An incident of severe crop loss due to spurious maize seed imported from India in 2009 induced a passionate debate on promoting locally improved varieties of crops in Nepal, shaping the seed policies of the government. Farmers from the Terai districts had been buying hybrid maize seeds from the bordering districts of India. In the winter of 2009, however, some of the varieties bought from across the border led to a heavy yield loss for thousands of Nepali farmers, as these varieties could not withstand the cold weather of the region (Adhikari 2014). The resulting uproar prompted the government to regulate non-domestic seed companies, which are now required to conduct multi-location trials for at least two seasons or years to ensure the performance and yield stability of these varieties before they can be registered in the seed quality control section (SQCC) of the Government of Nepal, and the maize hybrid seed sold in the Nepalese market.

ⁱⁱ In the Government of Nepal’s National Seed Vision (2013-25), the development of 12 hybrid maize varieties by the end of 2025 is envisaged. To meet this goal, the government actively promotes the development of the private seed sector in the country.

ⁱⁱⁱ Only six sample farmers (0.82%) grew both maize hybrids and OPVs on their farms in 2017 (i.e., partial adoption of the technology). The maize area allocated for hybrid maize was equal or greater than that allocated for non-hybrid maize varieties in all these farms. We considered them as the hybrid maize adopters in this study.

^{iv} The PCFE did not include expenditure on infrequent events such as marriage ceremonies.

^v The marginal effect of a dummy variable with the dependent variables in the log-form is calculated as $100 * [\exp(\text{Coefficient}) - 1]$, following Giles (2011).

^{vi} It should be noted that the IPWRA method captures only observed heterogeneity between hybrid maize adopters and non-adopters.